

Optimization of Various Cutting Parameters during Machining of 17-4PH Stainless Steel by Using Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL)

Md Irfan¹, Mohd. Faiz Khan²

¹M.Tech.(Production Engineering) Scholar, Mechanical Engineering department, Azad Institute of Engineering & Technology, Lucknow, India

²Assistant Professor, Mechanical Engineering department, Azad Institute of Engineering & Technology, Lucknow, India

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Abstract- Machining of different material with the conventional water soluble cutting oils have some challenges because of poor machinability characteristics. Many technology have been developed but minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) is the most frequent as it has merits over conventional cooling. The current work is focused upon the benefits of MQL over conventional cooling. Here the process parameter were compared for the machining of 17- 4PH stainless steel. It was observed that machining with MQL cooling technique gave better properties compare to conventional cooling. In addition to all those thing grey relational analysis (GRA) method was applied to determine the optimal solution. It clearly show that MQL environmental condition is a better way of machining 17-4PH stainless steel.

Keywords: Minimum quantity lubrication (MQL), conventional water soluble cutting oils, machining, 17-4PH stainless steel.

1. INTRODUCTION

Machining is one of the most important processes that is carried out in industry to develop product. Machining involves removal of materials from a workpiece using cutting tool with control. It has benefited in many ways by developing various product for us but has some limitations. The limitation includes generation of heat during machining which is a loss of supplied energy. The maximum energy supplied is converted into heat energy has to be minimized because the heat generation ultimately affect the product. There are various techniques have been developed to dissipate the generated heat during machining. The cooling techniques include flood cooling, cryogenic cooling and minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) system. Purpose of an ideal cooling technique includes-

1. Cooling the chip-tool and tool-workpiece interface.
2. Flushing the chip away from the machining zone.
3. Easy disposable.

Demerits of conventional cooling techniques:

1. It uses huge amount of coolant.
2. If operator repeatedly come in contact with coolant than the operator may develop skin problem.
3. There is disposal problem of the used coolant.

1.1.Flood Cooling

The conventional way of machining where a huge amount of coolant is used. Although it has been testified from past research as the better way of dissipating heat from machining zone but it has other drawbacks. The drawbacks because of which this cannot be preferred are serious as they causes skin disorder and environmental problem. Except cooling effect it doesnot fulfill any coolant property. It has more demerits compare to its benefits. There is always a problem of disposal of cutting fluid after machining which is hazardous to the environment.

1.2. Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL)

To minimize the set back in the flood cooling system anew technique has been developed which uses minimum quantity of cutting fluid.

The minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) has replaced the conventional way of cooling that is machining in flood cooling system. The flood cooling uses huge amount of lubricant yet does not satisfy all conditions of ideal cooling techniques. It cannot be easily disposable at the same time not environmental friendly. If one operator repeatedly come in contact with the flood cooling system operator may develop skin problem. As the name suggest MQL system uses less amount of lubricant and there is no disposal problem. MQL system includes mixture of high pressurized air with oil is being used as the lubricant in machining. The high pressurized (6bar) air is mixed with oil in the mixing chamber and directly supplied to the machining zone through nozzle. It is also called as “near dry machining” or “spatter lubrication” as it uses less amount of cutting fluid. No disposal problem in MQL system as the cutting fluid evaporated by gaining heat generated during machining.

The product obtained should be of good quality and the machining work need to be economical than only it will be considered as the process of machining as the best way of manufacturing product. To make the product of best quality it has to decrease the surface roughness at the same time minimize the cost of machining. Machining of best product includes good surface roughness and product of best desired shape and size for that purpose we need to increase the heat dissipation from machining zone to make a best product.

The methodology includes mixing of high pressurized (6bar) air with cutting fluid in a mixing chamber and directing the mixture to the cutting zone with a nozzle. Here the lubricant evaporated by gaining heat from the machining zone so it is basically an evaporative heat dissipation cooling techniques.

Advantages of MQL

- More effective as it directly applied to the machining zone instead of machining environment.
- Almost a dry process as it involves less amount of cutting fluid. Machining environment remain clean so safe working environment.
- It does the purpose of cooling and lubricating. Cutting fluid does the purpose of lubrication whereas high pressurized gas helps in heat dissipation.
- High pressurized gas flushes away the chip from machining zone so making chip disposal easy.
- It has been proved that machining done in MQL has better tool life and surface finish.

MQL is of two types –

1. Mixing inside the nozzle
2. Mixing outside the nozzle

Mixing inside the nozzle involves mixing of cutting fluid with compressed air inside the nozzle just before directing the lubricant to the machining zone. Here the mixing chamber is present inside the nozzle as shown in Figure 1.1 where high pressurized air and oil through the oil control valve supplied to the nozzle. In nozzle the entire mixture is carried out and it is directed to the machining zone.

Figure 1.1: MQL Mixing inside the Nozzle

In case of second one the conventional process of MQL cooling technique where the compressed air and the cutting fluid is mixed in a mixing chamber and the mixture is allowed to pass through the nozzle as shown in Figure 1.2. The mixing chamber where the mixture is done present in a separate place outside the nozzle and then it is supplied to the cutting zone.

Figure 1.2: MQL Mixing outside the Nozzle

1.3. Cryogenic Cooling

Cryogenic means working temperature is less than 123K. Liquid nitrogen is generally used as cryogenic material. It is present two-third of atmosphere gases. It boils at -198.79°C and melts at -210.01°C . Nitrogen is an odorless, colorless and non-toxic gas. The cryogenic coolant is supplied to the machining area where cutting temperature is high where it absorbs the generated heat there by reducing the cutting temperature. As this lower the cutting temperature it helps in better product manufacturing. Unlike MQL cryogenic cooling system cannot be set everywhere and it is costly from set up point of view.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The cutting velocity is one of the important parameter which affect the product and machining process. At constant depth of cut when feed was varied increase in cutting velocity led to decrease of cutting forces. The cutting forces increased with increase of cutting velocity because at high cutting velocity the heat generated was higher which resulted in tool wear acceleration as the diffusion and the adhesion wear increases and dominates. The accelerated tool wear hampered the cutting ability consequently increased in force [1]. When cutting velocity is 120m/min or high fully plastic chips are formed and there is bulk contact between tool rake surface and chips which prevent entering of any fluid into the chip tool interface resulting in increase of cutting force was investigated by B.Kumar, A. Sengole rayan volume 11, Issue 3 Ver. III(2014)[2]. Ling et al. observed that under all lubricating conditions cutting forces increases with increase in feed rate because as the feed rate increases the cutting area increases resulting in high cutting force [3].

Cutting forces decrease with speed under all lubrication conditions which is a significant effect on any machined components. MQL technique machining reduced the cutting forces because of reduction of friction because of lubrication effect of MQL jet (may be reduction in chip load) [4]. He et al. investigate that turning of bearing steel GCr15 at high cutting velocity under different cooling environment highly pressurised oil-mist mixture could penetrate into the cutting zone resulted in reduction of cutting forces compare to other cooling technique [5]. When Hadad and Sadeghi compared the machining of AISI 4140 steel under different cooling techniques observed that MQL gave the least value of cutting forces compare to Flood cooling and dry machining gave the Highest value of cutting forces [6]. Dhar et al. found that cutting force and feed force increased significantly under MQL environment with increase in cutting velocity [7].

Kishawy et al. experimented on aluminium alloy A365 on cutting environment of dry, flood and minimum quantity lubrication (MQL). The cutting forces obtained under MQL environment were marginally higher than the forces developed under flood cooling environment [10].

Li and Liang observed extensively study of machining parameters on process parameters under MQL technique machining. It was found that application of MQL during machining reduced the tangential cutting forces to a significant limit when machining is done at low cutting velocity [13].

2.1.Objective

From the literature review of past work it has observed that much work has been done on MQL. Using MQL techniques machining processes were reported like milling, turning, grinding etc. The effect of various cutting parameters has been investigated like cutting forces, co-efficient of friction, surface roughness and chip reduction coefficient. In the current work there is a comparison of various process parameter using MQL and flood cooling technique. To understand the benefits of MQL technique on 17-4 PH stainless steel the work is focused upon.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The turning experiment was done using a heavy duty lathe machine (Maker: Hindustan Machine Tools (HMT) Ltd.). The experiment was done on a cylindrical job of stainless steel (17-4PH). The workpiece on which the entire experiment was carried out with 42 mm in diameter and 400 mm in length. The turning experiment was carried out on conventional cooling conditions and minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) system conditions.

Figure 3.1: Experimental set-up for conventional cooling

Figure 3.2: Experimental set-up for MQL lubrication system

3.1.Workpiece and Tool material selection

All the turning operations were carried out on 17-4PH stainless steel. The metal is used as different aerospace application, chemical processing equipment. This also used as refining equipment for oil, petroleum and equipment for food processing. The chemical composition of the steel are shown in Table 3.1 and physical properties in Table 3.2.

Table 3.1: Chemical composition of 17-4PH stainless steel.

Elements	C	Mn	P	S	Si	Cr	Ni	Cu	Nb & Ta
Wt%	0.07	1	0.04	0.03	1	17	4	3-5	0.15-0.45

Table 3.2: Physical properties of 17-4 PH stainless steel

Physical Properties	Values
Density	7810kg/m ³
Poisson's Ratio	0.29
Elastic Modulus	196GPa
Ultimate Tensile Strength(UTS)	1103MPa
Yield Strength	1000MPa
Specific Heat	460J/kg-K
Thermal conductivity	18.3W/m-K
Rockwell Hardness	35

The machining was carried out using uncoated cemented carbide tool insert.

3.2.MQL set up

To conduct the turning experiment using minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) technique set up was developed and shown in Figure 3.3. The oil-mist mixture was supplied to the cutting zone with high pressure for machining.

Figure 3.3: Unit for MQL

3.3.MQL Techniques Working Principle

Highly compressed air is supplied into the air filter from a compressor through a solenoid valve. All the impurities are filtered that may present in the supplied air to keep it clean and dirt free. During this process oil control valves guided the oil to the mixing chamber. In mixing chamber the oil and the filtered air mixed to form oil-mist. The prepared oil-mist mixture is supplied to the cutting zone through a nozzle.

Experiment Design

The experimental design was based on Taguchi L9 orthogonal array for further optimization of result using grey relational analysis as shown in Table3.3. The turning process was carried out at a constant

length of cut of 15mm for all runs to study the effect of variations of cutting velocity, depth of cut and feed. The cutting velocity was varied over three levels: 40m/min, 70m/min and 100m/min. The depth of cut was varied as 0.5mm, 1mm and 1.5mm whereas the feed was varied as 0.08mm/rev, 0.14mm/rev and 0.20mm/rev.

Table 3.3: Experimental design using Taguchi L9 orthogonal array method.

Run no	Cutting velocity(m/min)	Feed(mm/rev)	Depth of cut(mm)
1	47	0.08	0.5
2	47	0.14	1
3	47	0.20	1.5
4	61	0.08	0.5
5	61	0.14	1
6	61	0.20	1.5
7	103	0.08	0.5
8	103	0.14	1.0
9	103	0.20	1.5

The turning of 17-4PH stainless steel was carried out under the following experimental conditions as summarized in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4: Experimental conditions for turning operation.

Workpiece Material	17-4PH stainless steel
Tool Insert	Uncoated cemented carbide insert
Cutting velocity(m/min)	47,61,103
Feed(mm/rev)	0.08,0.14,0.20
Depth of cut(mm)	0.5,1.0,1.5
Length of cut(mm)	15
Environment	MQL

During machining operation the cutting forces were measured as the output. The cutting forces were measured with the help of a dynamometer (maker: Kistler Instrument Co.) as shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Dynamometer for cutting forces measurement

After machining the workpiece surface roughness was measured using a profilometer (maker: Taylor Hobson: Sutronic) as shown in Figure 3.5. Surface roughness for each length of cut was measured by mounting the profilometer on the workpiece by using horizontal support. For each run chips were collected and chip thickness was measured to calculate chip-reduction coefficient with the help of digital vernier calliper.

Figure 3.5: Talysurf or Profilometer for surface Roughness measurement

3.4. Grey Relational Analysis

The grey relational analysis is a multi-response optimization technique. A black system means a system with no information whereas a white system represent availability of all the related information. Grey system is one which is in between of black and white system as all information are not available. To optimize a system using grey relational analysis (GRA) following steps are followed:

3.4.1. Normalization of Output

All the output responses were normalized between 0 and 1. Normalization was done according to 'higher the better characteristics' for responses which needed to maximize and 'lower the better' for the output responses which needed to minimize. But here cutting forces, surface roughness and coefficient of friction need to be minimized so 'lower the better' normalization system will be used. To normalize the output following equation will be used.

$$X_i(k) = \frac{\max y_i(k) - y_i(k)}{\max y_i(k) - \min y_i(k)} \quad (1)$$

Where $i=1,2,3,\dots,m$, $k=1,2,3,\dots,n$, m is the total number of experiment and n is number of output; $\max y_i(k)$ and $\min y_i(k)$ are the maximum and minimum values of output responses where $X_i(k)$ is the normalized value.

3.4.2. Calculation of Grey Relational Co-efficient

Grey relational coefficient is calculated for the normalized data of output responses. It is calculated by using the following equation.

$$\xi_i(k) = \frac{\Delta_{\min} - \zeta \Delta_{\max}}{\Delta_i(p) + \zeta \Delta} \quad (2)$$

$\xi_i(k)$ is the grey relational coefficient. ζ is the distinguishing factor whose value lies between 0 to 1, but for convenient taken as 0.5. Δ_{\min} and Δ_{\max} are the minimum and maximum normalized output.

3.4.3. Grey Relational Grade

Grey relational grade is calculated as sum of grey relational coefficient per number of output. Higher the value of grey relational grade high is the effect of parameter on the original experiment and vice

versa. Therefore, the combination with higher value of grey relational grade is the optimal combination to carry out the experiment. It is calculated using following relation:

$$y_i = (1/n) \sum_0^n \xi_i(k) \quad (3)$$

The grey relational analysis result is verified by conducting experiment with the corresponding optimal parameters.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After machining, the output responses were measured and tabulated as shown in Table 4.1 and 4.2.

Table 4.1: out responses for turning under flood cooling environment

Run No	Vc (m/min)	F (mm/rev)	t (mm)	Fz (N)	Fy (N)	Fx (N)	Ra (μm)	Rt (μm)	Rz (μm)	€	μ
1	47	0.08	0.5	220	134	105	2.266	14.66	11.33	2.4071	0.22534
2	47	0.14	1	442	190	243	1.866	15	9	2.2777	0.21116
3	47	0.2	1.5	651	215	392	1.933	13.66	10.666	1.8066	0.151722
4	61	0.08	1	338	170	223	1.933	19.66	10	2.21127	0.19187
5	61	0.14	1.5	540	222	375	2.266	18	12.666	2.36651	0.22097
6	61	0.2	0.5	290	180	120	3.4	12.66	11.33	1.65648	0.129468
7	103	0.08	1.5	354	220	335	1.866	13.33	9	2.56244	0.24138
8	103	0.14	0.5	207	187	100	1.666	13.66	9	1.4642	0.09781
9	103	0.2	1	524	212	261	1.866	12	9.666	2.1327	0.19429

Table 4.2: output responses for turning under MQL

Run No	Vc (m/min)	F (mm/rev)	t (mm)	Fz (N)	Fy (N)	Fx (N)	Ra (μm)	Rt (μm)	Rz (μm)	€	μ
1	47	0.08	0.5	210	130	100	3.666	29.66	12	1.993011	0.176913
2	47	0.14	1	421	186	258	1.6	11	9.666	2.529211	0.23803
3	47	0.2	1.5	674	237	400	1.733	10.66	9.33	2.18449	0.20044
4	61	0.08	1	307	160	225	1.533	12	7.33	3.3907	0.31323
5	61	0.14	8	520	214	379	1.8	10.66	9	2.11507	0.19216
6	61	0.2	0.5	280	170	116	3.466	28.66	16	2.0602	0.185419
7	103	0.08	1.5	334	200	325	1.2	11	6.33	2.30361	0.214067
8	103	0.14	0.5	220	165	105	1.266	7.66	6	1.61218	0.122514
9	103	0.2	1	512	220	273	1.933	11.33	9.333	1.03012	0.00761

Effect of cutting conditions on various machining characteristics under flood cooling and MQL cooling techniques.

The output responses were plotted for a various process parameters with machining parameters. The output responses considered were cutting forces, surface roughness and chip reduction co-efficient friction. Thus for output response effect of each process parameter was studied under all lubricating environment.

4.5 Grey Relational analysis (GRA)

From the analysis of above graphs, it is clear that MQL cutting environment is producing better result by minimizing cutting forces, surface roughness and chip reduction coefficient. The output table of the cutting conditions is shown in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Result table for MQL environmental conditions

Run no	V _c m/min	F mm/rev	Depth of cut mm	F _z N	R _a μm	μ
1	47	0.08	0.5	210	3.666	0.176913
2	47	0.14	1	421	1.6	0.23803
3	47	0.2	1.5	674	1.733	0.20044
4	61	0.08	1	307	1.533	0.31323
5	61	0.14	8	520	1.8	0.19216
6	61	0.2	0.5	280	3.466	0.185419
7	103	0.08	1.5	334	1.2	0.214067
8	103	0.14	0.5	220	1.266	0.122514
9	103	0.2	1	512	1.933	0.00761

After finding the output the output responses are normalized using equation 1 and tabulated in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5 Normalization of output responses

Run no	F _z (N)	R _a (μm)	μ
1	1	0	0.446034
2	0.545259	0.837794	0.246057
3	0	0.783861	0.369053
4	0.790948	0.864964	0
5	0.331897	0.756691	0.396146
6	0.849138	0.081103	0.418202
7	0.732759	1	0.324465
8	0.978448	0.973236	0.62403
9	0.349138	0.702758	1

From the normalized table grey relational co-efficient and grey relational grade are evaluate using equation 2 and 3 in Table 4.6. After calculating grey relational grade they are ranked according to their values. The combination which give highest value of grey relational grade is the optimal set of parameter for machining.

Table 4.6: Grey Relational analysis

Run no	F _z (N)	R _a (μm)	μ	Grey relational grade	Rank
1	1	0.333333	0.474399	0.602577	5

2	0.523702	0.755052	0.398742	0.559165	6
3	0.333333	0.698188	0.442107	0.49121	9
4	0.705167	0.787356	0.333333	0.608619	4
5	0.428044	0.672668	0.452958	0.51789	8
6	0.768212	0.352386	0.462194	0.527597	7
7	0.651685	1	0.425338	0.692341	2
8	0.958678	0.949192	0.570796	0.826222	1
9	0.434457	0.627162	1	0.687206	3

Mean effective plot of Grey relational analysis is shown in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Showing mean effect plot of grey relational co-efficient in MQL cutting technique.

From grey relational analysis it is cleared that the highest grey relational grade is obtained for run no.8. Whose $V_c = 103\text{m/min}$, $f=0.14\text{mm/rev}$ and $t=0.5\text{mm}$. The output corresponding to this run are $F_z = 220$, $R_a=1.266$, friction coefficient (μ) = 0.122514.

5. CONCLUSION

The current research work was carried out to study the comparison of conventional and minimum quantity lubrication during machining of 17-4PH stainless steel. The effect of various cutting parameters (cutting velocity, feed and depth of cut) on different process parameters studied with the help of column graph using Taguchi L9 orthogonal array method. After analysis following conclusions are drawn:

1. From the analysis cutting forces increase with increase in cutting velocity and feed rate.
2. However it was found that there was no significant changes in cutting forces in MQL cooling techniques compare to flood cooling.
3. The surface roughness decrease with increase of depth of cut and cutting velocity. MQL techniques obtained better result with respect to flood cooling.
4. The surface roughness increases in increase of feed rate. In this condition flood cooling system is better compare to MQL lubrication system.
5. Chip reduction co-efficient decrease with increase of cutting velocity and feed rate but increases with depth of cut. When MQL and flood cooling technique are compared MQL gave better result.

- The optimized process parameters of machining under MQL environment obtained as $V=103\text{m/min}$, $f=0.2\text{mm/rev}$ and $t=0.5\text{mm}$.

5.1. Contribution of Research work

The research mainly focused on importance of MQL turning on 17-4PH stainless steel compare to conventional cooling techniques. Hence it is recommended to use MQL for machining purpose of harden stainless steel material used in aerospace industries and other food and chemical processing and oil and petroleum refining equipment. MQL has significant effect on reducing the various output parameter of machining (cutting forces, surface roughness and chip reduction coefficient).

5.2. Recommendation for Future Work

The research indicated that MQL lubricating is the best machining environment to carry out any machining operation on 17-4PH stainless steel. It is the efficient way of cooling the machining process.

Future work on which further research can be done are:

- Influence of MQL on tool wear characteristics using Taguchi L27 orthogonal array method.
- Comparative study of and MQL for various process parameters (cutting forces, tool wear and surface roughness etc.). cryogenic cooling

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